

INTERFACE STRUCTURES IN AN β -SiC WHISKER-AL COMPOSITE

D. Z. Wang, Z. R. Liu and C. K. Yao
School of Materials Science and Engineering
Harbin Institute of Technology, 150001, P. R. CHINA

ABSTRACT

The interface nature, the orientation relationship of β -SiC whisker (β -SiC_w)-Al combination and the dislocation structures at β -SiC_w-Al interfaces in an β -SiC_w-Al composite have been observed by a high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM). It is shown that a quite good bonding between the whisker and the aluminum is achieved due largely to the atomic interactions between SiC and Al at interfaces. A preferred orientation relationship between the whisker and the aluminum is: $\{002\}_{\text{SiC}} // \{111\}_{\text{Al}}; \langle 110 \rangle_{\text{SiC}} // \langle 110 \rangle_{\text{Al}}$. The misfit dislocations cores are located in the whisker side with 3 interplanar spacings away from the interface.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recently years, interfaces in metal matrix composites have received much attention because they control the mechanical and thermal properties of the materials. A mechanism concerning the interface between the SiC and the Al matrix is put forward based on a scanning Auger microprobe analysis and a STEM analysis that there is penetration of the matrix into the reinforcement, and the diffusion bonding results in a high strength bond [1]. Inconsistent with this point of view, one conclusion based on a scanning Auger Multiprobe analysis and a STEM EDXA analysis is that the interaction between the whisker and the matrix aluminum (including the interface reaction and diffusion) has only taken place over a range of 50nm; Si and C appear not to diffuse into the Al matrix through the interface, and Al appears not to diffuse into the SiC whisker [2]. This difference may be explained by the following reasons: 1. the whisker surface has a shape of zigzag which may results in a overlap of the whisker and the aluminum at the interface in TEM specimens; 2. the spatial resolution of the energy dispersive X-ray analysis is about 30nm, which is equivalent to the width of 120 interplanar spacings of $(111)_{\text{SiC}}$. This will certainly has some effect on the results. However, a common point of view is that there are no reaction products, such as SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Al_4C_3 at the interfaces in SiC_w-Al composites [1, 2] except that the reinforcement is oxidized SiC particles [3]. It is also found that there are some orientation relationships between the SiC and the Al matrix, which were observed in an α -SiC-6061Al composite [4], but

few papers on this aspect in β -SiC-Al composites have been published. In addition, understanding of dislocation structures at interfaces in SiC-Al composites is still poorly understood, however, the plastic relaxation of thermal misfit stress directly depends on the dislocations at the interfaces.

The purpose of the present work was to determine in greater detail the interface structures including the orientation relationship and the dislocation structures in an β -SiC_w-Al composite.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The reinforcement used in this work is the β -SiC whisker. The matrix is commercial pure (99.75%)Al. An 22vol. % β -SiC_w-Al composite was fabricated by a squeeze casting method. The specimens, 3mm in diameter and 0.3mm thick, were cut from the as-cast composite by spark erosion. Subsequently, they were thinned by grinding and dimpling and were further thinned by ion milling with a 4.5KV argon ion beam under an angle of 7°.

The HRTEM observation was performed in a JEM 2000EX- II high-resolution electron microscope operated at 200KV.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 THE INTERFACE NATURE AND THE ORIENTATION RELATIONSHIP

Figure 1(a) shows a high-resolution electron micrograph of an β -SiC_w-Al interface. A high density of atomic steps with no reaction layer, void or amorphous can be found at the interface, so it can be concluded that a quite good bonding between the whisker and the aluminum is achieved. In Figure 2 the SiC structure is two dimensionally resolved. The arrangement of SiC is very regular, and there is no distortion of lattice, i. e. the lattice parameter of SiC is not changed, so we considered that the diffusion of Al into SiC did not occur, which is inconsistent with the results of [1]. This indicates that a match of SiC and Al atoms is formed at the interface, and a quite good bonding between the SiC and the Al is achieved due to the atomic bonding directly between SiC and Al.

Figure 1(b) is the electron diffraction pattern of the whisker in Figure 1(a), and Figure 1(c) is the electron diffraction pattern of the aluminum in Figure 1(a) after rotated the specimen in which the direction of the electron beam is rotated from $[\bar{1}10]_{\text{SiC}}$ to $[\bar{1}10]_{\text{Al}}$ with an angle of 6°. A preferred orientation relationship between SiC and Al can be deduced: $\{002\}_{\text{SiC}} // \{111\}_{\text{Al}}(2^\circ); \langle 110 \rangle_{\text{SiC}} // \langle 110 \rangle_{\text{Al}}(6^\circ)$.

This preferred orientation relationship may be analyzed as the following by using the schematic Figure 3, which shows the crystalline lattice pattern of the side surface of the β -SiC whisker contacting with the aluminum in Figure 1(a). The angle between $(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$

plane and $[111]$ direction, i. e. the growth axis of β -SiC whisker, is 9.74° . In the region free stacking faults and twins, in order to reduce the side surface area to decrease the growing energy, atomic steps will form on the side surface during the growth of whisker to ensure the side of whisker to parallel to the $[111]$ direction in total (although in some local parts the side of whisker is not parallel to the $[111]$ direction).

The steps are composed of three crystallographic planes, which indices are $(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})$, (111) and (002) , respectively, as shown in Figure 3. Those steps will become favorable sites for molten Al to nucleate. The closely packed plane and the colselly packed direction of Al are $\{111\}$ and $\langle 110 \rangle$, respectively. In order to decrease the systematic free energy in the process of the nucleation and growth of molten Al, the highest growth rate along $\{111\}_{Al}$ plane and $\langle 110 \rangle_{Al}$ direction can be achieved [5]. In order to form the preferred orientation relationship in the β -SiC_w-Al combination, it will also obey the law of the lowest free energy to choose which lattice plane and lattice direction of SiC to match $\{111\}_{Al}$ and $\langle 110 \rangle_{Al}$ due to the difference in lattice parameter between SiC and Al, i. e. the lowest mismatch must be achieved from the match between SiC and Al to reduce the interfacial energy. The interplanar spacing of $(111)_{Al}$ is 2.338 \AA , and the interplanar spacings of SiC corresponding to $(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})$, (111) and (002) are 2.51 \AA , 2.51 \AA and 2.71 \AA , respectively. The lattice plane mismatches (δ) between $(111)_{Al}$ and $(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})_{SiC}$, $(111)_{SiC}$ and $(002)_{SiC}$ can be given by:

$$\delta = |d_{SiC} - d_{Al}| / d_{Al}$$

i. e. 0.0736, 0.0736 and 0.0719, respectively. It is obvious that the mismatch between $(111)_{Al}$ and $(002)_{SiC}$ is the lowest. So in the view of energy it is favorable to choose $(002)_{SiC}$ as the substrate plane for molten Al to nucleate.

3.2 DISLOCATION STRUCTURES AT β -SiC_w-Al INTERFACE

In Figure 1(a) the interfacial misfit dislocations are clearly visible in the image. The core-like feature of the dislocations clearly indicates that the dislocation lines are parallel to the electron beam, i. e. $[\bar{1}10]$ direction. The strain field of the dislocation appears to be largely limited to the whisker side of the interface. The number of the $(002)_{SiC}$ lattice planes between two neighboring edge dislocations varies from 12 to 14 with an average value of 13. The average value of the spacing between the dislocations measured from the high-resolution image is about 3.138 nm .

The formation of the misfit dislocations in the whisker can be indicated in the schematic (Fig. 4). The lattice plane spacings of $(002)_{SiC}$ and $(111)_{Al}$ are incommensurate. However, due to relaxations along the interface, an epitaxial fit is achieved at the β -SiC_w-Al interface. The mismatch between $(111)_{Al}$ and $(002)_{SiC}$ is 0.0719, which is accommodated by localized misfit dislocations in the whisker. The geometrical spacing between the dislocations (D) can be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} D &= d_{Al} / \delta \\ &= 3.254 \text{ nm} \end{aligned}$$

Which is a good agreement to the value measured from the high-resolution image.

A common observation made for most metal-oxide interfaces, such as Nb-Al₂O₃[6], Ag-MgO[7], Nb-MgO[8], Cu-MgO and Pd-MgO [9] show that the misfit dislocations cores are located in the metal side away from the interface, and the "stand off" distance varies from systems to systems ranging from 1 to 3 interplanar spacings. Inconsistent with those observations, in the present work the edge dislocations cores are located in the SiC side (not in the Al side) with 3 interplanar spacings away from the β -SiC_w-Al interface. It is clear that the deformation of SiC is difficult due to its high elastic modulus, so the observation that the mismatch can be accommodated by misfit dislocation in the whisker probably indicates that the formation of this kind dislocation structures is favorable in the view of the systematic free energy, and in order to form the half atomic plane of the misfit dislocation a short distance diffusion for SiC in the surface of the whisker at high temperature may occur. It can also be deduced that the dislocation structure is favorable for the SiC to coordinate the Al to relax the thermal misfit stress to avoid the interface to be debonded during the relaxation, and is also favorable for the SiC to coordinate the Al to deform to avoid the damage of the interface when the composite has an applied stress. Further details about this aspect will be presented in another paper.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) There is no void, reaction layer or amorphous at β -SiC_w-Al interfaces in the β -SiC_w-Al composite. No diffusion of Al into SiC can be found passed through the interface. A quite good bonding between the whisker and the aluminum is achieved.
- (2) A preferred orientation relationship in the β -SiC_w-Al combination is : $\{002\}_{SiC} // \{111\}_{Al}; \langle 110 \rangle_{SiC} // \langle 110 \rangle_{Al}$.
- (3) The misfit dislocations cores are located in the whisker side with 3 interplanar spacings away from the interface.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by National Science Foundation of China, No. 59381002.

REFERENCES

1. R. J. Arsenault and C. S. Pande, Interfaces in metal matrix composites. Scripta Metall. **18**, 1131-1134(1984).
2. L. Cao, L. Geng, C. K. Yao and T. C. Lei, Interface in silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites. Scripta Metall. **23**, 227-230(1989).
3. H. Ribes and M. Suéry, Effect of particle oxidation on age hardening of Al-Si-Mg/SiC composites. Scripta Metall. **23**, 705-709(1989).
4. M. Van Den Burg and J. Th. M. De Hosson, Al-SiC interface structure studied by HREM. Acta Metall. Mater. **40**, Suppl. ,S281-S287(1992).

5. N. B. Min, Physical basic of the growth of crystalline. Shanghai Science and Technology Publishing House, Shanghai, China. P. 283(1982).
6. J. Mayer, G. Gutekunst, G. Möbus, J. Dura, C. P. Flynn and M. Rühle, Structure and defects of MBE grown Nb-Al₂O₃ interfaces. Acta Metall. Mater. **40**, Suppl., S217-S225(1992).
7. A. Trampert, F. Ernst, C. P. Flynn, H. F. Fischmeister and M. Rühle, High resolution transmission electron microscopy studies of the Ag/MgO interface. Acta Metall. Mater. **40**, Suppl., S227-S236(1992).
8. D. X. Li, P. Pirouz, A. H. Heuer, S. Yadavalli and C. P. Flynn, The characterization of Nb-Al₂O₃ and Nb-MgO interfaces in MBE grown Nb-MgO-Nb-Al₂O₃ multilayer. Acta Metall. Mater. **40**, Suppl., S237-3247(1992).
9. P. Lu and F. Cosandey, Dislocation structures at Cu-MgO and Pd-MgO interfaces. Acta Metall. Mater. **40**, Suppl., S259-S266(1992).

Figure 1. HRTEM image of the β -SiC_w-Al interface: (b) the electron diffraction pattern for the whisker in (a) and (c) the electron diffraction pattern for the aluminum in the near-interface-region after rotated from $[\bar{1}10]_{\text{SiC}}$ to $[\bar{1}10]_{\text{Al}}$ with an angle of 6°

Figure 2. HRTEM image of the β -SiC_w-Al interface

Figure 3. A schematic showing the structure of the side surface of β -SiC whisker

Figure 4. A schematic showing dislocations in the β -SiC whisker induced by the lattice misfit of $(002)_{SiC}$ and $(111)_{Al}$

